

New Distributional Records of Thrips from Jammu & Kashmir, India

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Abstract

Several field surveys have been conducted in the Jammu & Kashmir, Union territory of India, from 2019-2022. Eight thrips species: *Aeolothrips intermedius* Bagnall, *Anaphothrips sudanensis* Trybom, *Astrothrips tumiceps* Karny, *Bathrips melanicornis* (Shumsher), *Ernothrips lobatus* (Bhatti), *Neohydatothrips samayunkur* Kudô, *Scirtothrips oligochaetus* (Karny) and *Stenchaetothrips pteratus* Bhatti have been identified as new to this region. The species diagnosis, material examination, distribution and illustration of species are also provided.

Keywords: *New records, Thysanoptera, Thripidae, India, Jammu & Kashmir.*

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Introduction

Globally, around 6,402 species are known to exhibit in the insect order Thysanoptera (ThripsWiki, 2023). Members of the order Thysanoptera (thrips) are categorized into two suborders, nine families and six subfamilies (Mound *et al.*, 1980). The suborder Tubulifera, with 3,809 extant species, is considered the largest, followed by Terebrantia, with 2,593 species (ThripsWiki, 2023). Associates of this order are characterized by minute body size (~0.5-15mm), fringed wings and asymmetrical mouth parts (Mound and Marullo, 1996). They exhibit a wide array of feeding habitat ranging from fungivorous to phytophagous. Thrips are known for their pestiferous nature, causing severe damage to agricultural and horticultural crops (Singha *et al.*, 2018).

The Indian Thysanopteran fauna is limited to few studies with 739 species (Tyagi and Kumar, 2016). Several Indian states are still unexplored in terms of thrips diversity. Jammu and Kashmir (J&K) a Union territory in northern India, located in the Himalayan mountain ranges is known for its rich biodiversity. So far, only 20 species of thrips have been reported from this region (Tyagi and Kumar, 2016). During 2019-2022, several surveys have been conducted, and from the

collected samples, eight species were identified as new to this region. All these new distributional records belong to the families, Aeolothripidae (1) and Thripidae (7). The species are: *Aeolothrips intermedius* Bagnall, *Anaphothrips sudanensis* Trybom, *Astrothrips tumiceps* Karny, *Bathrips melanicornis* (Shumsher), *Ernothrips lobatus* (Bhatti), *Neohydatothrips samayunkur* Kudô, *Scirtothrips oligochaetus* (Karny) and *Stenchaetothrips pteratus* Bhatti.

Materials and Methods

Specimens were collected in 70% molecular grade alcohol from several host plants by beating method as suggested in previous studies (Singha *et al.*, 2021). The collected specimens were slide mounted using Nikon SMZ745T and photographed using Leica stereo zoom microscope (Leica DM-1000). Available morphological keys were used for species identification (Wilson, 1975; Bhatti, 1978, 1982; Masumoto and Okajima, 2002; Mound and Tree, 2009; Mound and Stiller, 2011; Alavi and Minaei, 2018). All the voucher specimens are labelled with unique registration number and deposited at National Zoological Collection, Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata.

Results

A total of 28 specimens of Thysanoptera were identified into eight species belonging to two families and eight genera. The identified species are recorded as new to the J&K region.

Systematic Account

Order THYSANOPTERA Haliday, 1836
Suborder TEREBRANTIA Haliday, 1836
Family AEOLOTHRIPIDAE Uzel, 1895
Genus *Aeolothrips* Haliday, 1836

Aeolothrips intermedius Bagnall, 1934
(Fig. 1)

1895. *Aeolothrips fasciata* var. *adusta* Uzel:
73.

Diagnostic characters: Female macropterous. Body dark brown with yellow antennal segment II apically; III distal third. Antennae 9-segmented; III and IV with linear sense cones; V distinctly shorter than IV and about as long as the terminal four segments together. Fore wing with 2 cross bands alternating with 3 clear areas. Metanotum with reticulation. Abdominal sternite VII with 2 minute discal setae.

Material examined: 2♀, India: Jammu and Kashmir, Kashmir, Kulgam, 1750m, 10.x.2021, general vegetation (Reg. No. 12358/H17 and 12360/H17), coll. by Shash Pal.

Distribution: India: Jammu and Kashmir (new record), Punjab, and Rajasthan.

Elsewhere: Austria, Canada, Estonia, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Kazakhstan, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Morocco, Norway, Poland, Russian Federation, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom and Ukraine.

Family THRIPIDAE Stephens, 1829
Subfamily PANCHAETOTHRIPINAE
Bagnall, 1912

Genus *Astrothrips* Karny, 1921
Astrothrips tumiceps Karny, 1923 (Figs. 2, 3)
1923. *Astrothrips tumiceps* Karny: 331.

Diagnostic characters: Female macropterous. Body yellowish brown with yellow antennae, all tarsi and apices of all tibiae. Fore wing pale apically with two dark cross bands. Head strongly reticulated. Antennae 7-segmented; III and IV each with simple sense cones. Pronotum with raised sculpture on lateral

margin of anterior half. Abdominal tergite II strongly constricted anterior marginally, with many claw-like microtrichia anterolaterally; IV-VII each with a pair of lateral sigmoidal setae; VIII with craspedum medially, toothed laterally; X with complete split.

Male macropterous, lighter than female. Abdominal sternites without pore areas.

Material examined: 1♀, 1♂, India: Jammu and Kashmir, Jammu, University of Jammu, 318m, 16.xii.2021, China berry (Reg. No. 12012/H17 and 12030/H17); 2♀, Jammu, University of Jammu, 311m, 18.i.2022, *Chrysanthemum coronarium* (Reg. No. 12011/H17 and 12021/H17); 1♂, 1♀, Jammu, University of Jammu, 318m, 16.xii.2022, China berry (Reg. No. 12100/H17 and 12101/H17); 1♀, Udhampur, 530m, 03.iv.2022, Curry leaves (Reg. No. 12344/H17); coll. by Shash Pal.

Distribution: India: Delhi, Jammu and Kashmir (new record), Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Bangladesh, Burma, Philippines and Indonesia.

Subfamily SERICOTHRIPINAE Karny, 1921
Genus *Neohydatothrips* John, 1929
Neohydatothrips samayunkur Kudô, 1995
(Fig. 4)

1995. *Hydatothrips* (*Neohydatothrips*)
samayunkur Kudo: 169.

Diagnostic characters: Female macropterous. Body bicoloured, with brown head, legs, pronotal blotch, abdominal tergites I-III and abdominal segments VII-X. Antennal segments I-II, VI-VIII; IV-V on distal half brown. Fore wing clavus brown with 2 cross bands alternating with 3 clear areas. Head with weak striations. Antennae 8-segmented; III and IV each with forked sense cones. Pronotum with transverse striations. Fore wing lower vein without setae. Abdominal sternites without discal setae.

Material examined: 2♀, India: Jammu and Kashmir, Doda, Paikul, 1740m, 13.viii.2021, Marigold (Reg. No. 12345/H17 and 12346/H17); 1♀, Doda, Paikul, 1760m, 30.viii.2021, Marigold (Reg. No. 12177/H17);

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1♀, Doda, Paikul, 1760m, 30.viii.2021, grass (Reg. No. 12202/H17); 1♀, Jammu, University of Jammu, 313.95m, 05.iii.2021, general vegetation (Reg. No. 12255/H17); 1♀, Kathua, 365m, 27.iv.2022, rose (Reg. No. 12093/H17); 1♀, Reasi, Chassana, 1320m, 20.iv.2022, mulberry leaves (Reg. No. 12090/H17), coll. by Shash Pal.

Distribution: India: Andaman Island, Arunachal Pradesh, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir (new record), Karnataka, Maharashtra, Manipur and Uttarakhand.

Elsewhere: Australia, Brazil, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Japan, Mexico, Sri Lanka and U.S.A.

Subfamily THRIPINAE Stephens, 1829

Genus *Anaphothrips* Uzel, 1895

Anaphothrips sudanensis Trybom, 1911

(Fig. 5)

1911. *Anaphothrips sudanensis* Trybom: 1.

Diagnostic characters: Female macropterous. Body bicoloured, with brown head, antennal segments I-II, V-VIII and abdominal segments I-II, VII-X. Antennae 8-segmented; III-IV each with short forked sense cone. Mesonotum with transverse lines of sculpture. Metanotum with irregular reticulation. Abdominal tergites with dentate microtrichia posterolaterally absent medially.

Material examined: 1♀, India: Jammu and Kashmir, Kathua, 353m, 27.iv.2022, rose (Reg. No. 12123/H17), coll. by Shash Pal.

Distribution: India: Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Delhi, Jammu and Kashmir (new record), Karnataka, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Punjab, Sikkim and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, China, Cuba, Cyprus, Egypt, Indonesia, Israel, Morocco, New South Wales, Philippines, Puerto Rico, Somalia, South Africa, Sri Lanka, Sudan, Taiwan, Trinidad.

Genus *Bathrips* Bhatti, 1962

Bathrips melanicornis (Shumsher, 1946)

(Fig. 6)

1946. *Taeniothrips melanicornis* Shumsher: 179.

Diagnostic characters: Female macropterous.

Body yellow with light brown patches in ocellar triangle, pronotum and metanotum. Antennae brown. Fore wing darker. Abdominal tergites II-VII with T-shape patches covering almost the entire anterior half of each tergum. Antennae 8-segmented; III and IV each with a forked sense cone. Metanotum weakly reticulated medially. Abdominal tergite IX with posterior pair of campaniform sensilla.

Material examined: 1♀, India: Jammu and Kashmir, Doda, Govt. Degree College, 1107m, 01.i.2021, rose (Reg. No. 12095/H17); 1♀, Doda, Paikul, 1720m, 30.viii.2021, grass (Reg. No. 12173); 1♀, Jammu, Botanical garden of University of Jammu, 313.95m, 12.iv.2020, lemon grass (Reg. No. 12107/H17); 1♀, Jammu, University of Jammu, 313.95m, 23.xii.2021, China berry (Reg. No. 12174/H17); 1♀, Jammu, Botanical garden of University of Jammu, 313m, 07.iii.2022, grass (Reg. No. 12020/H17); 1♀, Udhampur, Mand, 530m, 03.iv.2022, curry leaves (Reg. No. 12109/H17); 2♀, Udhampur, Mand, 530m, 30.iv.2022, *Cannabis sativa* (Reg. No. 12172/H17 and 12184/H17), coll. by Shash Pal.

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Jammu and Kashmir (new record), Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Burma, China, East Timor, Indonesia, Malaysia, Myanmar, Taiwan and Thailand.

Genus *Ernothrips* Bhatti, 1967

Ernothrips lobatus (Bhatti, 1967) (Fig. 7)

1926. *Thrips immsi* Bagnall: 110.

Diagnostic characters: Female macropterous. Body brown, antennal segment III yellow; mid, hind tibiae and all tarsi yellow. Fore wing with basal fourth paler. Head with transverse striations. Antennae 7-segmented; III and IV each with a forked sense cone. Metanotum with longitudinal striations. Abdominal tergites II-VIII sculptured laterally absent medially.

Material examined: 1♀, India: Jammu and Kashmir, Jammu, Botanical Garden University of Jammu, 315m, 07.iii.2022, white rose (Reg. No. 12022/H17), coll. by Shash Pal.

Figures 1-10: 1. *Aeolothrips intermedius*, female; 2. *Astrothrips tumiceps*, female; 3. *Astrothrips tumiceps*, male; 4. *Neohydatothrips samayunkur*, female; 5. *Anaphothrips sudanensis*, female; 6. *Bathrips melanicornis*, female; 7. *Ernothrips lobatus*, female; 8. *Scirtothrips oligochaetus*, female; 9. *Stenchaetothrips pteratus*, female; 10. *Stenchaetothrips pteratus*, male.

Distribution: India: Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir (new record), Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh.

Elsewhere: China, Indonesia, Thailand, Japan, Taiwan and Malaysia.

Genus *Scirtothrips* Shull, 1909

Scirtothrips oligochaetus (Karny, 1926)

(Fig. 8)

1926. *Anaphothrips oligochaetus* Karny: 201

Diagnostic characters: Female macropterous. Body yellow, antennal segments III-VIII brown. Abdominal sternites III-VI with shaded antecostal ridge. Mesonotum with transverse lines of sculpture. Metanotum anterior half with transverse striations, posterior half with irregular elongate reticulations. Abdominal tergite VIII with several rows of microtrichia anteromedially; IX posteromedially. Abdominal sternites IV-VI with microtrichia covering median area except on anterior half.

Material examined: 1♀, India: Jammu and Kashmir, Jammu, University of Jammu, 313.95m, 23.xii.2020, white rose (Reg. No. 12201/H17), coll. by Shash Pal.

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Jammu and Kashmir (new record), Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Cabo Verde, Ethiopia, Nigeria, Malaysia, Tanzania, U.A.E., West Indies and Yemen.

Genus *Stenchaetothrips* Bagnall, 1926

Stenchaetothrips pteratus Bhatti, 1982

(Figs. 9, 10)

1982. *Stenchaetothrips pteratus* Bhatti: 409.

Diagnostic characters: Female macropterous. Body yellow except with brown abdominal segments VII-X. Antennal segments I-IV yellow, V-VIII brown VII brown with few exceptions. Antennae 7-segmented; III and IV each with a forked sense cone. Metanotum with longitudinal striations. Abdominal tergite with short irregular teeth posterolaterally.

Male concolourous to female. Abdominal segment brown on VII; V distally. Abdominal sternites III-IV each with a small pore area. Parameres not dilated apically.

Material examined: 1♀, 1♂, India: Jammu and Kashmir, Udhampur, Mand, 530m, 30.iv.2022, *Cannabis sativa* (Reg. No. 12347/H17 and 12179/H17), coll. by Shash Pal.

Distribution: India: Jammu and Kashmir (new record) and Himachal Pradesh.

Elsewhere: No record.

Discussion

Thrips are recognized for their substantial ecological and economic significance. The current state of knowledge regarding the Thysanoptera fauna in India is limited, primarily as a result of insufficient field surveys and a dearth of taxonomic expertise. The primary objective of this study was to address the existing knowledge gap in thrips research by contributing eight novel distributional data from the Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir, India. This study proposes the implementation of comprehensive surveys to better investigate the diversity of thrips within the region.

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